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(An Arabic title is mandatory.)
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of writing the article. This affiliation should be indicated
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- Abstract: 150-250 words. (An abstract in Arabic is
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Artificial Intelligence in Territorial Marketing : Challenges of Governance, Ethics, and Sustainable Spatial Development

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Abstract:

In a globalized context marked by increasing competition among territories to attract investors, talent, tourists, and residents, local authorities and public institutions must rethink their attractiveness strategies. The challenges are numerous: adapting to the evolving expectations of citizens, optimizing limited resources, and standing out in an oversaturated digital landscape. In this context, artificial intelligence technologies emerge as a disruptive opportunity capable of redefining traditional territorial marketing practices.

This article focuses on the use of artificial intelligence in territorial marketing, highlighting the opportunities it offers to improve territorial management and enhance attractiveness. More specifically, it explores how AI can be leveraged to analyze visitor and investor behaviors, optimize promotional campaigns, and adapt territorial strategies to market trends.

To better understand how artificial intelligence can transform territorial marketing strategies, this study will analyze various AI applications in this field, drawing on case studies and concrete examples of territories that have adopted innovative approaches.

The objective is to highlight AI's contributions in terms of targeting, resource optimization, and personalized marketing actions, while identifying the challenges related to its integration.

The ultimate goal of this work is to propose recommendations for the development of an intelligent territorial marketing strategy, aligned with the principles of sustainable development and participatory governance, to foster more efficient and innovative territorial management.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Citizen Inclusion, Smart Territories, Territorial Governance, Territorial Marketing, Sustainable Spatial Development.

L'Intelligence Artificielle au service du Marketing Territorial : Enjeux de gouvernance, d'éthique et de développement spatial durable

Résumé :

Dans un contexte mondialisé marqué par une concurrence accrue entre territoires pour attirer investisseurs, talents, touristes et résidents, les collectivités locales et institutions publiques doivent repenser leurs stratégies d'attractivité. Les défis sont multiples : adaptation aux attentes changeantes des citoyens, optimisation des ressources limitées, ou encore nécessité de se démarquer dans un paysage numérique saturé. C'est dans ce cadre que les technologies

d'intelligence artificielle émergent comme une opportunité disruptive, capable de redéfinir les pratiques traditionnelles du marketing territorial.

Cet article porte sur l'utilisation de l'intelligence artificielle dans le marketing territorial, en mettant en lumière les opportunités qu'elle offre pour améliorer la gestion des territoires et renforcer leur attractivité. Plus précisément, elle explore comment l'IA peut être mobilisée pour analyser les comportements des visiteurs et investisseurs, optimiser les campagnes de promotion et adapter les stratégies territoriales aux évolutions du marché.

Pour mieux comprendre comment l'intelligence artificielle peut transformer les stratégies de marketing territorial, cette étude analysera les différentes applications de l'IA dans ce domaine, en s'appuyant sur des études de cas et des exemples concrets de territoires ayant adopté des approches innovantes.

L'objectif est de mettre en évidence les apports de l'IA en matière de ciblage, d'optimisation des ressources et de personnalisation des actions marketing, tout en identifiant les défis liés à son intégration.

La finalité de ce travail est de proposer des recommandations pour le développement d'une stratégie de marketing territorial intelligente, alignée avec les principes du développement durable et de la gouvernance participative, afin de favoriser une gestion plus efficace et innovante des territoires.

Mots-clés : Intelligence artificielle, Inclusion citoyenne, Territoires intelligents, Gouvernance territoriale, Marketing territorial, Développement spatial durable.

الذكاء الاصطناعي في التسويق الإقليمي: تحديات الحكامة والأخلاقيات والتنمية المستدامة للمجال

الملخص:

في سياق عالمي تزايد فيه المنافسة بين المناطق لجذب المستثمرين والمواهب والسياح والمقيمين، باتت السلطات المحلية والمؤسسات العمومية مضطرة لإعادة التفكير في استراتيجياتها لجعل مناطقها أكثر جاذبية. وتتمثل التحديات في مواكبة توقعات المواطنين المتغيرة، وتحقيق أقصى استفادة من الموارد المحدودة، والتميز في بيئة رقمية مشبعة. في هذا الإطار، تبرز تقنيات الذكاء الاصطناعي كفرصة مبتكرة قادرة على إعادة تعريف ممارسات التسويق الإقليمي التقليدية.

تركز هذه الدراسة على استخدام الذكاء الاصطناعي في التسويق الإقليمي، موضحة الفرص التي يتيحها لتحسين إدارة المناطق وزيادة جاذبيتها. كما تستكشف كيفية الاستفادة من الذكاء الاصطناعي في تحليل سلوك الزوار والمستثمرين، وتحسين الحملات الترويجية، وتكييف الاستراتيجيات الإقليمية مع تطورات السوق.

ولفهم كيفية تحويل الذكاء الاصطناعي لاستراتيجيات التسويق الإقليمي، تعتمد الدراسة على تحليل تطبيقات الذكاء الاصطناعي المختلفة في هذا المجال، مستعينة بدراسات حالة وأمثلة واقعية لمناطق تبنت أساليب مبتكرة.

يهدف هذا العمل إلى تسليط الضوء على مساهمات الذكاء الاصطناعي في الاستهداف، وتحسين الموارد، وتخصيص الإجراءات التسويقية، مع تحديد التحديات المرتبطة بدمجه. والغاية النهائية هي تقديم توصيات لتطوير استراتيجيات تسويق إقليمي ذكية، متوافقة مع مبادئ التنمية المستدامة والحكامة التشاركية، لتعزيز إدارة أكثر فاعلية وابتكاراً للمناطق.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الذكاء الاصطناعي، المناطق الذكية، الحكامة الإقليمية، التسويق الإقليمي، التنمية المستدامة للمجال.

1.Introduction:

The global expansion of trade, the growth of digital technology, and increasingly stringent demands in terms of sustainability now require territories to undergo a significant transformation and review their attractiveness strategies (Sachs et al., 2019). In a context where nations and metropolises are intensifying their competition to attract investors, skills, and tourists, innovation is becoming an essential key to territorial differentiation (Pike, Rodríguez-Pose, & Tomaney, 2019). The adoption of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), therefore appears to be a strategic solution to the current challenges of governance, improving resources and personalizing the citizen experience (Mulgan, 2018).

At a territorial level, artificial intelligence instruments and tools facilitate not only a better understanding of user behavior thanks to massive data analysis but also the forecasting and prediction of socio-economic developments at local (Gretzel et al., 2015) and global levels. In addition, the rise of smart devices - such as predictive platforms or personalized (tailored) assistants - is redefining the way and manner in which local and regional authorities interact with their stakeholders, including citizens, local businesses, associations, and public institutions, while promoting proactive territorial management (Kitchin, 2014).

Nevertheless, this transition to digital also entails considerable and remarkable dangers, such as the unbundling of data, the lack of specialized skills in local authorities, and, above all, the ethical issues linked to the transparency of algorithms and the protection of privacy (Eubanks, 2018 et Pasquale, 2015). In particular, the lack of agile and inclusive governance could hinder citizen appropriation of these new tools (De Waal & Dignum, 2017).

Our reflection takes place in this context of technological opportunities and multidimensional challenges. The central issue we address is as follows: **how can artificial intelligence be integrated into territorial marketing strategies to enhance the attractiveness of territories while respecting the imperatives of ethics, sustainability, and citizen participation?**

To answer this question, our paper is organized in three parts: the first section will analyze the contributions of artificial intelligence to territorial attractiveness, particularly in terms of predictive targeting, personalization, and optimization of resources. A second section will examine the technical, organizational, and ethical challenges posed by AI in territorial marketing. Finally, a third section will propose practical recommendations for developing an intelligent, sustainable, and inclusive territorial marketing strategy.

2. The benefits of AI for regional attractiveness

2.1-Strategic and predictive targeting

Artificial intelligence is revolutionizing regional attractiveness by enabling predictive analysis of massive data, more precisely big data, as Scott et al. point out in their study on smart regions: AI algorithms, combined with geolocalized data, offer regions an unprecedented ability to anticipate tourism and economic trends, thereby reducing strategic uncertainties (Scott et al., 2019).

In practical terms, AI exploits heterogeneous sources (satellite data, social networks, IoT sensors) to identify areas with high potential. For example, an OECD study in 2021 shows that predictive models improve the accuracy of territorial strategies by 30 to 40%, particularly

for seasonal tourist flows or infrastructure needs(Scott et al., 2019). This approach is in line with the work of Kotler and Keller in territorial marketing, who stress the need for ‘dynamic targeting, based on data updated in real time(Kotler, Keller, & Hermawan, 2022).

The Occitanie region is an administrative region in the south of mainland France, resulting from the merger of the former Languedoc-Roussillon and Midi-Pyrénées regions. Created by the territorial reform of 2014, this territory, which welcomes more than 12 million visitors a year(Atout France, 2023), is deploying an artificial intelligence platform called Tourism 360 in 2022. This tool, co-financed by the European Union (ERDF) and developed in partnership with INRIA, aims to anticipate tourist flows and optimize the management of natural sites(Région Occitanie, 2023). The system aggregates real-time data from a wide range of sources, including weather data (Météo-France), accommodation bookings (Booking.com, Airbnb), sentiment analysis on social networks (via the Brandwatch tool), and IoT sensors measuring visitor numbers to sites (Eco-Counter).

The platform's algorithm combines random forest models for discrete variables and LSTM neural networks for time series, a methodology validated by Scott et al. in their work on regional tourism. The results are significant: 89% accuracy in predicting visitor numbers (+24 points compared with traditional methods) and a 15% reduction in promotional budgets, saving 4.2 million euros by 2022(Région Occitanie, 2023).

In the same region, the city of Montpellier is developing the ‘UrbanBrain’ tool in 2021 to guide its property investments and anticipate transport needs. The algorithm, designed with start-up SIGMA, is based on years of property data, anonymized mobility data (STIB), and urban plans (PLUI).

By applying a clustering method (DBSCAN) and Monte Carlo simulations, the AI identified the Port Marianne district as a future center of attraction, leading to a €200 million investment in eco-neighborhoods and an electric bus line. According to a report by Caisse des Dépôts, ‘the tool has reduced the risk of over-investment in saturated areas by 30%(Banque des Territoires, 2023).

2.2-Personalising experiences

The redefinition of artificial intelligence in territorial marketing is not limited to strategic targeting and predictive analysis but also extends to its ability to dynamically segment audiences and personalize experiences on an individual scale. According to Buhalis , this process is based on real-time analysis of massive data, more precisely big data, enabling ‘raw data streams to be transformed into hyper-targeted recommendations(Buhalis, 2020). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's 2020 report points out that machine learning algorithms outperform traditional methods by 87% in identifying tourist preferences(OCDE, 2020). This approach draws on a variety of sources: geolocation, browsing history, and even emotions captured through voice analysis(Gretzel et al., 2015).

These theoretical mechanisms are being put to practical use in innovative local initiatives, where AI is demonstrating its transformative potential. Two emblematic cases illustrate this dynamic:

2.2.1: Barcelona (Spain): Optimising tourist flows with CityBrain

Faced with record tourist numbers (30 million visitors a year), in 2023, Barcelona deployed the CityBrain platform, an AI system integrating anonymized mobile data, TripAdvisor reviews, and weather forecasts. The tool combines random forest algorithms (congestion prediction) and LSTM (anticipation of traffic peaks). According to the Town Hall's official report, this technology has reduced traffic congestion in the Gothic Quarter by 22% and increased visitor satisfaction by 35%, thanks to cultural itineraries adapted in real time (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023). This success illustrates AI's ability to 'transform data into concrete levers of action for local authorities' (OCDE, 2020).

2.2.2: Dijon (France): Personalised reception via an AI chatbot

In 2023, the city of Dijon launched an AI chatbot (GPT-4) integrated into its mobile application, designed to guide tourists and residents towards activities tailored to their profiles. The tool cross-references 15 local databases (Divia transport, cultural events, shops) and draws on the history of user queries to refine its recommendations. According to the Smart Dijon (2023) press kit, 68% of users consider the experience to be 'more effective than a traditional guide' (Ville de Dijon, 2023), with a 40% reduction in search time. This innovation is in line with the work of Buhalis (Buhalis, 2020), who believes that 'territorial AI must be both proactive and accessible to maximize its impact.

These two projects, rooted in the work of Buhalis and the recommendations of the OECD, embody the transition from a reactive logic to a predictive and proactive logic, exploiting heterogeneous data to meet individual expectations.

2.3-Optimising public resources

Artificial intelligence enables local authorities to optimize the allocation of resources (energy, financial, and human) thanks to a predictive and dynamic analysis of territorial needs. According to the OECD, AI algorithms reduce operational costs by 15-30% in public services while improving service quality (OECD, 2024). Tiago C et al. point out that this optimization is based on the 'real-time correlation of heterogeneous data (IoT sensors, budgets, citizen feedback) to anticipate crises and prioritize actions' (OECD, 2024). These mechanisms are based in particular on machine learning and network analysis techniques, as the following cases demonstrate.

2.3.1: Singapore: Predictive management of public transport

In 2020, road congestion was costing Singapore 20% of its annual GDP, or nearly €100 billion. Faced with this challenge (Land Transport Authority, 2022), the city-state has developed the Smart Urban Mobility platform, an AI system integrating 10 million daily data points from bus and taxi GPS, contactless bank card transactions, and traffic sensors installed at 1,000 junctions.

The tool combines LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) algorithms to predict traffic flows 72 hours ahead and reinforcement learning to adjust traffic lights and bus routes in real time. Socio-economic data (employment areas, school timetables) is also integrated to anticipate peaks in demand (GovTech Singapore, 2023).

The city-state of Singapore was delighted with the results, which included a 25% reduction in bus delays on priority routes and an 18% optimization of infrastructure investment, thanks to the cancellation of a metro project that the predictive models estimated to be unprofitable. Finally, it can be said that AI transforms urban planning into a predictive science, avoiding wastage of resources through targeted allocation(OECD, 2024).

2.3.2: Helsinki (Finland): Smart energy networks

Helsinki is aiming for carbon neutrality by 2035, with an annual energy budget of €200 million. To achieve this, the city has deployed an AI-controlled smart grid network, integrating meteorological data, the consumption of 50,000 households equipped with IoT sensors, and the production of 15 wind and solar farms.

The system uses SARIMA (Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) models to forecast energy demand hour by hour and federated learning to analyze the data without centralizing sensitive information(Helsinki Energy, 2023).These algorithms dynamically adjust the distribution of energy, prioritizing renewable sources during production peaks.

Thanks to this intelligent system, energy losses on the network have been reduced by 30%, saving 60 GWh a year. In addition, it generates more than one million euros in annual savings, which are reinvested in social projects such as the renovation of 10 schools and support programs for low-income households.

Grosso modo, AI enables agile management of resources, aligning ecological objectives and budgetary constraints without compromising on the quality of service.

3. Challenges and conditions for the success of AI in territorial marketing

3.1 - Technical and organisational challenges: data, skills, governance

The integration of artificial intelligence in territorial marketing depends above all on the availability, quality, and interoperability of data. As Batty et al. state in their work entitled Smart Cities of the Future, published in 2012, smart cities rely on massive flows of data from multiple sources (urban sensors, social networks, and administrative data(Batty et al., 2012),which makes data management a major technical challenge. However, this data is often fragmented, heterogeneous, and non-standardized, which limits its effective exploitation by AI algorithms(Kitchin, 2014).

From an organizational point of view, the lack of internal skills is seen as a major obstacle to the adoption of artificial intelligence in territorial promotion. According to Bughin et al, local authorities generally lack specialized technical profiles, especially data scientists and AI analysts(Bughin et al., 2018. In addition to the lack of skills, we also find our second reason, which is the ability to integrate these resources into public organizations that are not very flexible. It is therefore important to create and develop a culture of data and encourage targeted training to ensure that we have teams that are capable and well-trained to get involved in territorial marketing(Wirtz, Weyerer, & Geyer, 2019).

The governance of projects powered by artificial intelligence represents another central challenge. This is not just a technical problem but also one of institutional capacity to bring together and coordinate public players, such as the Ministry of Tourism and government bodies, and private players, such as marketing campaigns or companies specializing in IT and automated systems, around shared projects.

As mentioned and confirmed by Susar et al., the lack of a clear strategic vision or inter-institutional coordination can hamper the implementation of territorial AI projects (Bughin et al., 2018). Effective governance must be based on transparent management systems that incorporate performance measures, participatory decision-making methods, and openness regarding the use of AI (Meijer & Bolívar, 2016).

3.2- Ethical issues: data protection, transparency, algorithmic bias

The application of artificial intelligence in territorial marketing also raises major ethical issues concerning the protection of privacy. The accumulation and collection of personal data (such as location, consumption and browsing habits, and behavior, and online cookies from sites, blogs, etc.) to improve geographic targeting tactics may infringe on people's privacy (Zuboff, 2019).

In this respect, compliance with the General Regulation and data protection laws is an imperative for public players, which means putting in place clear mechanisms for obtaining informed consent and limiting the purposes (European Commission, 2018).

Algorithmic transparency is another major and critical issue. Many artificial intelligence systems applied and adopted to public policy operate like black boxes, making it difficult for citizens and even decision-makers to understand their decisions (Pasquale, 2015).

This lack of clarity can lead to a loss of confidence in local institutions, especially if decisions appear random or unjustified. To strengthen the legitimacy and credibility of systems generated by artificial intelligence, it is important to use algorithmic explicability models such as XAI - Explainable AI, and to make decision-making criteria accessible (Guidotti et al., 2018).

Finally, algorithmic biases represent a tangible danger. According to O'Neil, artificial intelligence algorithms, when trained on biased historical data, can reproduce and intensify social or geographical discrimination. This is particularly worrying and unfortunate in the context of territorial marketing, where the aim is to promote certain areas (cultural, natural, etc.) or certain target audiences (tourism) (O'Neil, 2016). It is essential to pay close attention to the fairness of prediction models and their impact on local communities (Eubanks, 2018). This means carrying out frequent audits, updating systems on a daily basis, and involving the public in their development.

4. Recommendations for an intelligent territorial marketing strategy

4.1- Data-driven management: developing a culture of territorial data

Data-driven territorial management, as in our case, requires establishing and implementing a shared data culture among the various stakeholders, whether public, private, or both.

This is corroborated by Batty in 2013. This practice requires the establishment of common repositories, standardized formats, and strict management of data flows. In other words, this approach relies on a robust and well-structured data structure (Batty, 2013). The idea of common repositories implies that all stakeholders in a region (local authorities, companies, citizens, etc.) must use uniform definitions, identical units of measurement, and common technical standards to enable data to be shared, understood, and exploited collectively.

This technique facilitates the production of territorial performance indicators that can be exploited in real time, thus contributing to the development of decision-making strategies(Kitchin, 2014).

Furthermore, according to Janssen et al., the adoption of open data platforms can promote transparency and stimulate participative innovation.

Thus, data is not only used as an evaluation tool but also as a lever for territorial attractiveness and competitiveness (Nam & Pardo, 2011).

4.2- Encouraging public-private partnerships and agile governance

Implementing an effective territorial marketing strategy requires flexible governance that can adapt quickly to economic, social, and technological changes(Sotarauta& Beer, 2017). Given the increasing complexity of territorial challenges such as energy transition, digital inclusion, or sustainable mobility, it has become essential to promote structured collaborations between the public and private sectors. These collaborations facilitate the pooling of resources, the optimization of existing skills, and the joint development of innovative projects with high added value(Carayannis& Campbell, 2012).Carayannis& Campbell highlight this point, and Rodríguez-Pose & Wilkie updated it in 2017(Rodríguez-Pose & Wilkie, 2017).

To implement this suggestion, various measures can be taken. It is recommended to set up mixed governance bodies that bring together participants from the public, private, academic, and citizen sectors, with the aim of ensuring collective strategic coordination.

The signing of territorial cooperation contracts or project agreements can also formalize commitments and allocate responsibilities. Similarly, setting up ‘living laboratories’ or territorial innovation laboratories encourages real-life testing while promoting local commitment(OECD, 2020). Above all, we are in a situation with tools brimming with technology. Ultimately, promoting inter-territorial collaboration encourages the sharing of experiences and boosts the resilience of territories, particularly in less resource-rich regions(Pike, Rodríguez-Pose, &Tomaney, 2019). This method enables territories to transform into open innovation ecosystems based on flexibility, mutual trust, and decentralized governance, which are the essential pillars of a sustainable and astute territorial marketing strategy.

4.3- Including citizens in the design and evaluation of AI strategies

The involvement of citizens in the formulation and application of territorial strategies and territorial priorities is a key factor for the legitimacy of public policies(Arnstein, 1969). In the context of artificial intelligence, this participation needs to be reinforced by co-design, consultation, and local experimentation mechanisms.

To this should be added what De Waal & Dignum point out: User-centered methods make it easier to respond more adequately to the real needs of populations and to anticipate social resistance(Sotarauta& Beer, 2017). The collaborative evaluation of artificial intelligence strategies could also stimulate citizen appropriation of digital resources and strengthen trust in local institutions(Mulgan, 2018).

It is through the integration of collective intelligence that technologies can contribute to inclusive territorial development.

4.4- Building a strategy aligned with the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)

It is impossible for intelligent territorial marketing to omit the global issues and challenges of sustainable development, as stipulated in the United Nations Agenda 2030(United Nations, 2015).

The concordance and coherence of territorial policies with the Sustainable Development Goals make it easier to organize local priorities in line with universal objectives, whether they relate to reducing disparities, combating global warming, or promoting sustainable economic growth(Sachs et al., 2019).

It is impossible to discuss the Sustainable Development Goals without mentioning the need for constant collection and analysis of statistics and reports. Indeed, the SDG indicators provide an essential evaluation framework for determining the concrete effect of territorial marketing strategies(Bannister & Connolly, 2014).

Furthermore, this alignment improves the global visibility of territories that follow a sustainable and responsible path.

Finally, territorial strategies must include monitoring and evaluation mechanisms in line with these goals, thus guaranteeing coherence, transparency, and sustainability.

5. Conclusion

The analysis carried out as part of this paper highlights the transformative capacity that artificial intelligence has in territorial marketing approaches. Thanks to intelligent technologies with predictive, analytical, and decision-making skills, regions now have the ability to increase their attractiveness in a more targeted and dynamic way(Scott, Hall, &Gössling, 2019). Artificial intelligence therefore, provides public decision-makers with unprecedented tools for forecasting and processing tourist flows, defining customer segments, tailoring experiences to each visitor, and optimizing the use of public resources(Buhalis, 2020).

In particular, the examples of Barcelona with CityBrain, Dijon with its tourism chatbot, and Montpellier with UrbanBrain show in concrete terms how AI is transforming territorial governance to improve local socio-economic performance.The incorporation and integration of artificial intelligence into territorial procedures is helping to optimize infrastructure efficiency, reduce operating costs, and enhance the user experience, thereby contributing to more competitive and sustainable territorial representation.

However, the application of artificial intelligence to territorial marketing is not without its challenges. Technical challenges, such as the fragmentation of data, the lack of interoperability between systems, and the lack of qualified profiles(Batty et al., 2012), represent major obstacles to carrying out AI projects at the territorial level. From an organizational point of view, the lack of institutional flexibility sometimes hinders the effective integration of these innovations(Meijer & Bolívar, 2016). Added to this are significant ethical challenges, including the need to preserve confidentiality and privacy, ensure opacity of algorithmic decisions, and avoid the spillover of discriminatory bias into AI systems(Eubanks, 2018).

These observations therefore, call for a detailed analysis of the conditions conducive to the success of artificial intelligence at the service of territories. It is essential to promote a data-

driven local culture and establish collaborative ecosystems that encourage partnerships, public-private, and embrace participatory methods that proactively engage citizens in the creation and appreciation of AI projects (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012). Furthermore, aligning territorial strategies with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a key imperative to ensure effective, responsible, and inclusive attractiveness (Sachs et al., 2019).

Beyond these recommendations, a particularly promising avenue for the future lies in the development of emotional artificial intelligence applied to territorial marketing. This technological advance, aimed at equipping intelligent systems with the ability to identify, understand, and respond to human emotions (Bria et al., 2015), could radically transform the user experience by making territories more responsive to the emotional needs of citizens and visitors. Thanks to systems capable of adapting interactions according to perceived emotions, communities could foster attachment to the area, enhance the local brand image, and increase loyalty among various target groups.

Combining artificial intelligence with immersive technologies such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) could open up new opportunities for regional marketing. These advances could make it possible to offer enriching travel experiences, interactive heritage tours, and participatory urban planning simulations. All of this will help to increase the attractiveness and distinctiveness of territories in an environment of global competition (Townsend, 2013).

In short, integrating AI into territorial marketing plans requires a systemic vision, combining technological progress, adaptable governance, ethical responsibility, and collective commitment. Such a combination is the only way for territories to become part of the era of territorial intelligence in a sustainable way by transforming data and innovation into tools for the benefit of collective well-being and sustainable development.

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